

Lorentz Transformation of Photon EM Field Energy and Poynting Momentum and Phase Invariance Physically Defining a Wave

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In general, given a charge at rest, its EM field energy $\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 \int E'' \cdot E'' dv$, where E'' is electric field in the rest frame, does not transform as the fourth component of a 4-vector. In the moving frame, the field energy is: $\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 \int E \cdot E + \frac{1}{2} \mu_0 \int B \cdot B$ and the Poynting momentum $\frac{1}{\mu_0} \int dv E \times B$.

In the moving frame, one also has the equations: $\square^2 \phi = 1/(4\pi \epsilon_0) \rho$ charge density and $\square^2 A = \mu_0 \epsilon_0 \int v \rho$ charge density for a point charge. If one sets the charge density to 0, then $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ is a solution for ϕ , where $\omega/k=c$, the speed of light in a vacuum.

In a previous note, we argued that one may set $\phi'' = \exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ and $A'' = \exp(-i\omega t + ikc)$ (1,1,1) and obtain E'' electric and B'' magnetic fields perpendicular to each other and to the direction of motion, i.e. x direction and of equal magnitude. For these solutions, one may show that: $\int dx \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 \int E \cdot E + \frac{1}{2} \mu_0 \int B \cdot B / \int dx$ is ω (we set $c=1$), and that the average Poynting momentum is k . Thus, there is a physical link for the parameters ω, k . For a rest charge, however, these energies and momentum do not transform like a 4-vector. We show, however, that for the ϕ'' and A'' chosen above, the em field energy and Poynting momentum do transform as 4-vectors.

It is already known that $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ is a solution in one frame, and $\exp(-i\omega' t' + ik' x')$ in another, such that $c = \omega/k = \omega'/k'$, but that does not prove that one has a Lorentz invariant phase, By directly transforming ϕ'' and A'' , however, one may show explicitly that em field energy and poynting momentum, equal to ω and k do transform as a 4 -vector. This means that $-i\omega t + ikx$ is a Lorentz invariant, i.e. the phase is a Lorentz invariant. We argue there is physical relevance to the phase of $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$, namely that one has physical implications to the wave solution because the top of a crest in one frame is the top of a crest in another.

EM Field Energy of a Rest Point Charge and Lorentz Transformations

It is well-known in the literature that the EM field energy of a rest charge:

$$\int \epsilon_0/2 E'' \cdot E'' dv \quad ((1)) \quad \text{where } E'' \text{ is the electric field in the rest frame}$$

does not transfer as the fourth component of a 4-vector. Thus, one has to be careful regarding the transformation of:

$$\left\{ \frac{1}{\mu_0} \int dv E'' \times B'', \frac{\epsilon_0}{2} \int E'' \cdot E'' dv + \frac{1}{2\mu_0} \int B'' \cdot B'' dv \right\} \quad ((2))$$

Solution for No Sources

In general, one has the Lorentz invariant equations:

D'Alembertian $\phi'' = 1/(4 \cdot 3.14 \epsilon_0)$ charge density " ((3a)) and

D'Alembertian $A'' = \epsilon_0 u_0 / (4 \cdot 3.14 \epsilon_0)$ charge density" v ((3b)) where v is velocity

We suggested in a previous note, that one may consider the solution, for no sources: (Going forward, we set $c=1$ and drop ϵ_0 and u_0 because $c=1/\sqrt{\epsilon_0 u_0}$).

$\phi'' = \exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ ((4a)) and $A'' = \exp(-i\omega t + ikx) (1, 1, 1)$ ((4b))

At this point, ω, k are simply parameters. One may explicitly calculate E'' and B'' to find:

$E'' = \{ 0, i\omega \exp(-i\omega t + ikx), i\omega \exp(-i\omega t + ikx) \}$ and $B'' = \{ 0, -ik \exp(-i\omega t + ikx), ik \exp(-i\omega t + ikx) \}$ ((5))

Here $\exp() = \exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$

E'' and B'' have the same magnitude and are perpendicular to each other and the direction of motion.

Out of curiosity, one may take the real parts of E'' and B'' and compute the EM field energy for a half cycle divided by Integral dx over this half cycle as well as the Poynting momentum integral over a half cycle divided by integral dx of the half cycle. This yields:

Field Energy = ω and Poynting momentum integral = k ((6))

Note: Integral $\cos(kx) \cos(kx) dx +$ Integral $\sin(kx) \sin(kx) dx =$ Integral dx ((7))

with the two summands on the LHS being equal.

Thus, ω, k are no longer simple parameters, but have physical meaning. This does not guarantee, however, that they Lorentz transform as a 4-vector. We, however, show explicitly that they do.

$|A| = |g - vg| |A''|$ where $g = 1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ ((8))
 $|\phi| = |g - vg| |\phi''|$

Similarly: $x = gx'' - vgyt''$ and $t = -vgx'' + gt''$ $\rightarrow x' = g(x + vt)$ and $t' = g(vx + t)$ ((9))

Thus, $\phi = g(1 - v) \exp(-i\omega t'' + ikx'')$ and $A = \{g(1 - v) \exp(), \exp(), \exp()\}$ ((10))

And $-i\omega t'' + ikx'' = x' ig \omega(-1 - v) - twg(1 - v)$ ((11))

$E = \{0, -i\omega g(1 - v) \exp(-i\omega t'' + ikx''), -i\omega g(1 - v) \exp(-i\omega t'' + ikx'')\}$ ((12a))

$B = \{0, -kig(1 - v) \exp(), ikig(1 - v) \exp()\}$ ((12b))

Thus, in the moving frame, E and B are perpendicular to each other and the direction of motion x and have the same magnitude.

One may now take the real parts of E and B (in the moving frame) and compute:

$$\left\{ \int dx \frac{1}{2} E \cdot E + \frac{1}{2} B \cdot B \right\} \int dx = 2gk(1-v)(1-v) \int \cos(Kx)\cos(Kx) dx / \int dx \text{ for } t=0.$$

where $K = g(1-v)k$

One may use: $\frac{1}{K} \int \cos(Kx)\cos(Kx) dKx + \frac{1}{K} \int \sin(Kx)\sin(Kx) dKx = \int dKx$

and note that the two summands on the LHS have the same value.

Thus:

$$\text{Field energy} = gk(1-v)^2 (.5) = g(1-v)w \quad ((13))$$

Similarly, one may show that the Poynting momentum integral is: $k g(1-v) \quad ((14))$

Given ((13)) and ((14)), it follows that the Poynting momentum integral and the field energy transform as a 4-vector, thus, (k,w) transforms as a 4-vector.

(k,w) is usually called the momentum and energy of a photon.

It seems, however, that there is another consequence of the above result, namely that $-wt+kx$ in $\exp(-iwt+ikx)$ is a Lorentz invariant. In other words, phase is Lorentz invariant. We suggest that this implies there is physical significance to the phase. Just as an invariant charge value has physical meaning, the top of a crest in one frame is the top of a crest in another. We suggest that this means there is physical manifestation of the wave, i.e. interference of photons in this case.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the em field energy and Poynting momentum integral do not necessarily transform as a 4-vector. We consider the D'Alembertian $\phi'' = 0$ and D'Alembertian $A'' = 0$, i.e. with sources set equal to 0. In a previous note, we showed that $\phi'' = \exp(-iwt+ikx)$ and $A'' = \exp(-iwt+ikx) (1,1,1)$ (with $c=1$ and ϵ_0 and μ_0 dropped) lead to E and B fields perpendicular to each other, of equal magnitude and perpendicular to the direction of motion x. One may further show that the EM field energy of this solution is w and the Poynting momentum integral k.

One may then Lorentz transform A'' and ϕ'' and rewrite x'' , t'' in terms of x,t. It follows that the Lorentz field energy and integral of the Poynting momentum transform as a Lorentz 4-vector. Thus (k,w) in the " frame transforms via a Lorentz transform to new parameters k_1, w_1 in the moving frame. k,w behave like the momentum and energy of an object with rest mass in terms of Lorentz transformations. As a result, $-wt+kx$ is Lorentz invariant. We suggest that this has

physical implications, namely that the wave mathematical structure has physical relevance because the top of a crest in one frame is the top of a crest in the moving frame. Thus the idea of wave mechanics, i.e. interference etc seems to be physical which experiments on photons bear out.